

**Manganese(II), Cobalt(II), Nickel(II) and
Copper(II) Complexes with *p*-Tolyl-2-
furylgyoxalimine**

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In this paper we report the preparation and characterisation of Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes with Schiff bases derived from 2-furylgyoxal and *p*-toluidine. These complexes were also screened for antibacterial activity against a number of microorganisms and have exhibited potential activity¹.

Experimental

Schiff base has been prepared by refluxing (~4 h) equimolar 2-furylgyoxal² (1.24 g, 10 mmol) and *p*-toluidine (1.07 g, 10 mmol) in ethanol. The Schiff base (black, m.p. 105°) thus obtained was filtered and recrystallised from ethanol.

Bis(p-tolyl-2-furylgyoxalimine) manganese(II) chloride: To an ethanolic solution of $MnCl_2 \cdot 4H_2O$ (1.98 g, 10 mmol) was added an ethanolic solution of Schiff base (4.26 g, 20 mmol). The reaction mixture (~60 ml) was refluxed for ~4 h and then reduced to one-third of its volume. The dark red crystals obtained on cooling were recrystallised from 95% ethanol.

The similar procedure was adopted for the synthesis of all the metal compounds reported, but for the sake of brevity only one reaction has been discussed in detail.

The electronic spectra and molar conductances of the complexes were measured in DMF solvent. Magnetic movements were determined at room

temperature (30°). The ir spectra (KBr) were recorded in the range 4 000–200 cm^{-1} .

Antibacterial screening of the Schiff base and its metal compounds were done by the disc-diffusion technique at the S. M. S. Medical College, Jaipur. The disc of 5mm dia. was used for the control.

Results and Discussion

The analytical results indicate 1 : 2 metal – ligand stoichiometry for all the complexes. The complexes are soluble in DMF, DMSO, nitrobenzene and chloroform. The molar conductance values of 0.001 *M* solutions of the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes in DMF were found to be 40.0, 39.0, 39.58 and 43.75 $\Omega^{-1} cm^2 mol^{-1}$, respectively, indicating the non-electrolytic nature of the complexes³. The μ_{eff} values of 6.03, 4.0, 2.98 and 1.82 B.M. for the Mn^{II} , Co^{II} , Ni^{II} and Cu^{II} complexes, respectively, were slightly higher than the corresponding spin-only values showing the spin-free octahedral environment around the metal ions⁴.

The Schiff bases ligand showed two strong ir bands at 1 620 (C=N) and 1 660 cm^{-1} (C=O). These bands show the negative shift in the spectra of the corresponding metal complexes⁵ except in $[Ni(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$, where it shifted to the high frequency region⁶, indicating the involvement of C=N and C=O groups in complexation. The position of C–O–C bands remains unaltered at 1 000 cm^{-1} even on complexation. Three new ir bands appearing at 510–570, 410–460 and ~280 cm^{-1} in the complexes were assigned to ν_{M-N} , ν_{M-O} and ν_{M-Cl} stretching modes, respectively⁷. The electronic spectra of the Mn^{II} complex $[Mn(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$ in solution, showed a number of bands of weak intensities: (26 315 cm^{-1}) ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g({}^4D)$, (24 390) ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4E_g$, ${}^4A_{1g}({}^4G)$ and (13 513) ${}^6A_{1g} \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}({}^4G)$.

The values of 10 *Dq*, Racah parameters^{8,9} *B* and *C* and other ligand field parameters were calculated: 10 *Dq*, 302.50; *B*, 275; *C*, 4 328; *F*₂, 893.28; *F*₄, 109.28; β , 0.34; λ , 67.5; *f*, 0.35; and *hx*, 9.42. Due to increased delocalisation, β was found to be less

TABLE I—ANTIBACTERIAL ACTIVITIES* OF *p*-TOLYL-2-FURYLGLYOXALIMINE AND THE COMPLEXES IN DMF AFTER 2 DAYS

Temp = 37 ± 1°

Compd.**	Organisms in different concn. ($\mu g cm^{-2}$)														
	<i>E. coli</i>			<i>S. aureus</i>			<i>B. subtilis</i>			<i>S. veridance</i>			<i>P. vulgaris</i>		
	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500	25	100	500
$C_{12}H_{11}O_2N$	—	4.0	10.0	—	—	6.0	—	6.0	12.0	—	4.0	12.0	—	6.0	8.0
$[Mn(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$	—	4.00	10.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	8.0	—	—	2.0	—	—	4.0
$[Co(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$	—	—	—	—	6.0	12.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	—
$[Ni(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$	—	—	2.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	2.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	—
$[Cu(C_{12}H_{11}O_2N)_2Cl_2]$	—	—	2.0	—	—	4.0	—	—	6.0	—	—	8.0	—	—	2.0

* Inhibition zone diameter in mm. ** $C_{12}H_{11}O_2N = p$ -Tolyl-2-furylgyoxalimine
DMF was used as a control and showed nil activity against all the bacterials.

than one in the complex. The lower value of f and higher value of hx indicated covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond.

Cobalt(II) complex showed three d-d bands in the region 11 494, 16 129 and 19 230 cm^{-1} which may be attributed to transitions, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4A_{2g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^4T_{1g}(F) \rightarrow {}^4T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$, respectively. The values of ν_1 , ν_2 and ν_3 may be obtained by Konig's equations¹⁰. The values of 10 Dq and B were calculated¹¹. The ratio $\nu_2(\text{obs})/\nu_1(\text{calcd.})$ was found to be 2.01 as required for octahedral cobalt(II) complexes. Calculated 10 Dq value was in good agreement to that determined by $\nu_2(\text{obs}) - \nu_1(\text{calcd.})$. The β_{35} value in the range 0.69-0.99 clearly indicated the partial covalent character of the metal-ligand bond.

The electronic spectrum of the complex, $[\text{Ni}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ was consistent with octahedral geometry. The d-d bands at 13 698, 23 895 and 28 571 cm^{-1} were assignable to the ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{2g}(F) (\nu_1)$, ${}^3A_{2g}(F) \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(F) (\nu_2)$ and ${}^3A_{2g} \rightarrow {}^3T_{1g}(P) (\nu_3)$ transitions, respectively¹². The inter-electronic repulsion parameter B and other ligand field parameters 10 Dq , β_{35} and λ were calculated as usual^{13,14}. The ν_2/ν_1 ratio was found to be 1.74 as against 1.80 (theoretical)¹⁴. The lower value of ν_2/ν_1 indicated distortion of the octahedral geometry. The β_{35} value in the range 0.53-1.20 indicated covalent nature of the metal-ligand bond.

Three shoulder bands at 13 157, 14 925 and 25 641 cm^{-1} in the electronic spectra of the complex $[\text{Cu}(\text{C}_{13}\text{H}_{11}\text{O}_2\text{N})_2\text{Cl}_2]$ were assigned to ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2A_{1g}$, ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2B_{2g}$ and ${}^2B_{1g} \rightarrow {}^2E_g$ transitions, respectively, showing distorted octahedral geometry¹⁵ in the complex.

Antibacterial screening: All the compounds were tested for their antibacterial activity by disc-diffusion method in DMF and found to be active against *E. coli*, *S. aureus*, *B. subtilis*, *S. veridence* and *P. vulgaris*. The highest dilution of the test compounds which inhibited the visual growth of the test organisms was taken as the minimum inhibitory concentration ($\mu\text{g cm}^{-2}$). The results are presented in Table 1.

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Cobalt(II), Nickel(II), Copper(II), Zinc(II), Cadmium(II) and Mercury(II) Complexes with *N,N'*-Bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane

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IN continuation of earlier studies¹⁻⁴ on the Schiff base complexes of divalent metal ions, the present communication reports the synthesis of a new (O, N, N, O) tetradentate Schiff base ligand, *N,N'*-bis(benzoin)-4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane and its complexation behaviour with Co^{II} , Ni^{II} , Cu^{II} , Zn^{II} , Cd^{II} and Hg^{II} .

Experimental

All the chemicals were of A.R. grade.

Preparation of ligand: To the ethanolic solution of benzoin (4.2 g, 0.02 mol) and 4,4'-diamino-3,3'-dimethyldiphenylmethane (2.3 g, 0.01 mol), anhydrous sodium acetate (4 g) was added and the reaction mixture refluxed over a water-bath for 2 h. The hot solution was then poured into ice-cold water with stirring when the light yellow coloured Schiff base separated out. It was allowed to stand for 24 h and then filtered, washed with water, dried and recrystallised from ethanol (95%), m.p. 115° (Found: C, 82.67; H, 5.92; N, 4.28. $\text{C}_{43}\text{H}_{38}\text{O}_2\text{N}_2$ calcd. for: C, 84.03; H, 6.18; N, 4.56%).

Preparation of complexes: To the ethanolic solution of metal chlorides (0.01 mol), the ligand solution (0.01 mol) in ethanol was added separately and the reaction mixture refluxed over a water-bath for ~0.5 h. On cooling, concentrated NH_4OH was added dropwise with stirring when the metal